

OBJECTIVE ONE

Examine your background on marine sciences.

To start your journey you must demonstrate the basic knowledge of these scientific issues.

“It's time to play!”

OBJ 1 – 1

LOGICA: Match Game v.2

GAMES RULES: Match each item with the corresponding rank

QUESTION: Link the kind of water with the appropriate % over the world:

Fresh water	2,5%
Surface fresh water (included in the fresh water %)	0,3%
Groundwater (included in the fresh water %)	29%
Permanent glaciers and snow (included in the fresh water %)	68,9%
Salt water	97,5%

GAME RULES
Match each item with the corresponding rank

5/28
Objective 1 | Objective 2 | Objective 3

QUESTION
Build the family tree of this bird matching each item with the corresponding rank:

Species

Genus

Family

Kingdom

Animalia

Ardeidae

Egretta

Egretta thula

CHECK CONTINUE

OBJ 1 – 2

LOGICA: Match Game

GAMES RULES: Match each item with the corresponding rank

QUESTION: Identify True or False in oceanography.

The relative proportions among the various ions in all the seas of the world are almost the same even if their total quantity varies considerably from area to area. True

The relative proportions among the various ions in all the seas of the world are different even if their total quantity it is equal in each area. False

Evaporation is a physical phenomenon that regenerates only water, while all dissolved, suspended or diffused substances remain at sea. True

The average salinity of the Mediterranean Sea is 37 ‰. True

The average salinity of the seas is 33 ‰. False

GAME RULES
Match each item with the corresponding rank

QUESTION
Build the family tree of this bird matching each item with the corresponding rank:

Species		Animalia
Genus		Ardeidae
Family		Egretta
Kingdom		Egretta thula

CHECK CONTINUE

OBJ 1 – 3

LOGICA: Match Game

GAMES RULES: Match each item with the corresponding rank

QUESTION: Identify True or False in oceanography.

In very cold seas, where large masses of water freeze during the winter, there are increases in salinity because the solidification in ice that affects the water partially excludes the salts. True
Organisms living on very salty conditions belong to the extremophile category, more specifically they are halophiles. True

Oxygen is completely soluble in water. False

The Biochemical Oxygen Demand measures the biological oxygen demand during some organic matter oxidation processes. True

OBJ 1 – 4

LOGICA: Match Game

GAMES RULES: Match each item with the corresponding rank

QUESTION: Link the main sectors of the Blue Economy with the appropriate activity or subject:

Mineral Resources

Coastal and Maritime Tourism

Biotechnology

Aquaculture and fisheries

Renewable Energy

Transport

Shipbuilding and ship repair

Marine Technologies

Seabed mining

Whale watching

Bioremediation

Food safety

Tidal turbine

Motorways of the Sea

Naval/Nautical material

Innovative marine sensors and platforms

GAME RULES
Drag and drop words in the proper box

QUESTION
Identify Individual VS Population traits.

Gene pool	Assimilation efficiency	Brood size	Birth rate
Home range	Reproductive strategy	Breeding behaviour	Body size
Individual		Population	

CHECK CONTINUE

OBJ 1 – 5

LOGICA: Drag&Drop v.2

GAMES RULES: Drag and drop words in the proper box

QUESTION: Identify marine sources of Renewable Energy versus non-Renewable Resource

Manganese nodules

Hydrocarbon deposits

Massive sulphide deposits

Sand and gravel

Waves

Tides

Currents

Thermal and salinity gradients

non-Renewable Resources

non-Renewable Resources

non-Renewable Resources

non-Renewable Resources

sources of Renewable Energy

sources of Renewable Energy

sources of Renewable Energy

sources of Renewable Energy

OBJ 1 – 6

LOGICA: Match Game

GAMES RULES: Match each item with the corresponding rank

QUESTION: Identify True or False for the marine litter

Marine litter is any persistent, manufactured or processed solid material discarded, disposed of or abandoned in the marine and coastal environment. True

The ratio of microplastics particle to zooplankton in the northwestern Mediterranean is 1:2. True

The organic pollutants can bond in high concentrations to microplastic particles and enter the food chain through the marine fauna which take up the plastic while feeding. True

In general, 80% of discharges of plastic originate onshore, that is from rivers or large landfills in coastal areas, but also the shipping and fishing industries contribute to the pollution. True

OBJ 1 – 7

LOGICA: Match Game

GAMES RULES: Match each item with the corresponding rank

QUESTION: Identify True or False for the marine litter

Common plastics such as polyethylene are notable for their high density and thus sink at the ocean bottom. False

Microplastics are only formed as a result of physical, biological and chemical degradation of macro-plastic particles. False

Marine litter include semi-solids remains of for example mineral and vegetable oils, paraffin and chemicals that sometimes litter sea and shores. False

The ratio of microplastics particle to zooplankton in the northwestern Mediterranean is 1:10. False

OBJ 1 – 8

LOGICA: Match Game

GAMES RULES: Match each item with the corresponding rank

QUESTION: Identify True or False for the Research Infrastructures (RIs)

RIs can be a single resource at a single location True

RIs are used by the research communities to conduct top-level research True

RIs include innovative scientific equipment, scientific data, computing capacities and software systems. True

RIs play an increasing role in the advancement of knowledge and technology and their exploitation. True

RIs don't propel cooperation across the scientific fields as well as national borders. False

RIs don't share scientific data and information. False

The education and dissemination are not one of RIs objectives. False

OBJ 3 - 5

LOGICA: Short Question

GAMES RULES: Choose the correct answer

QUESTION: Identify if the climate change study evaluate long term, short term variability or both

The climate of a particular region is determined through analysis of Climatological variables in a region over a period of 30-years or greater. The parameters measured include Temperature, Wind speed, Relative humidity, Rainfall, Atmospheric pressure, Sunshine hours.

Climate change

Long term variability

Long term variability, Short term variability, Both

OBJECTIVE TWO

Learn more about marine science.

Now it's time to learn more through the knowledge of parameters and relatives instruments of measure.

GAME RULES

Match each item with the corresponding rank

3 / 28

Objective 1 | Objective 2 | Objective 3

QUESTION

What are the correct match between listed species characteristics and their reported descriptions?

Emphasises that a species consists of organisms potentially capable to breed producing fertile off spring

Phylogenetic affinity

Emphasises that populations of a same species may diverge when exposed to different selective pressures

Evolution

Emphasises the degree of relationships occurring among taxa

Reproductive isolation

CHECK

CONTINUE

OBJ 1 – 7

LOGICA: Match Game

GAMES RULES: Match each item with the corresponding rank

QUESTION: Match instrument with correspondent variable

CTD	Temperature
ADCP	Horizontal velocity components of Marine currents
Seismometer	Ground velocimeter
Fluorimeter	Chlorophyll concentration
CTD	Conductibility
Turbidimeter	Turbidity

The screenshot shows a word game interface. In the top left, there is a circular icon with a grid and a hand cursor. To its right is a white box titled "GAME RULES" containing the text "Identify the exact word by guessing letters in the answer". In the top right, there is a progress bar showing "15 / 28" and three objective indicators: "Objective 1", "Objective 2" (highlighted in green), and "Objective 3". On the left side, a white box titled "QUESTION" contains the text: "A system, in the meaning of physics, including the community and the abiotic factors interacting in an area:". The main area features a horizontal line for the word and a keyboard with letters in rounded boxes. The keyboard has three rows: the first row contains Q, W, E, R, T, Y, U, I, O, P; the second row contains A, S, D, F, G, H, J, K, L; and the third row contains Z, X, C, V, B, N, M. A grey "CONTINUE" button is located at the bottom right of the main area.

OBJ 2 - 5

LOGICA: Hangman

GAMES RULES: Identify the exact word that describe an instruments that is passively transported by the currents

DRIFTER

GAME RULES
Drag and drop words in the proper box

QUESTION
Identify Natural disturbances VS Anthropogenic pressures.

Cutting down forest	Hurricane devastation	Mining	Spontaneous fires
Tsunami	Overfishing	Species immigration	Species introduction
Natural disturbance		Anthropogenic pressures	

CHECK CONTINUE

OBJ 1 – 7

LOGICA: Drag&Drop v.2

GAMES RULES: Drag and drop words in the proper box

QUESTION: Identify parameters measured respectively by physical and biological oceanography

Sea waves	physical oceanography
Tide	physical oceanography
Sea level	physical oceanography
Temperature	physical oceanography
Phytoplankton	biological oceanography
Benthos	biological oceanography
Primary production	biological oceanography
Nutrients	biological oceanography

GAME RULES
Identify the exact word by guessing letters in the answer

QUESTION
A system, in the meaning of physics, including the community and the abiotic factors interacting in an area:

15 / 28
Objective 1 | **Objective 2** | Objective 3

Q W E R T Y U I O P
A S D F G H J K L
Z X C V B N M

CONTINUE

OBJ 2 - 5

LOGICA: Hangman

GAMES RULES: Identify the exact word that describe an instruments that travels underwater without requiring input from an operator

AUV

OBJ 1 – 8

LOGICA: Drag&Drop v.2

GAMES RULES: Drag and drop words in the proper box

QUESTION: Identify parameters measured respectively by geophysics and by chemical oceanography

Magnetic field intensity

Electro-Magnetic wave velocity

Gravity acceleration

Oxygen concentration

Methane concentration

geophysics

geophysics

geophysics

chemical oceanography

chemical oceanography

GAME RULES
Identify the exact word by guessing letters in the answer

QUESTION
A system, in the meaning of physics, including the community and the abiotic factors interacting in an area:

15 / 28
Objective 1 | **Objective 2** | Objective 3

Q W E R T Y U I O P
A S D F G H J K L
Z X C V B N M

CONTINUE

OBJ 2 - 5

LOGICA: Hangman

GAMES RULES: Identifies the exact word that describes an instrument that travels underwater guided by a cable

ROV

OBJ 1 – 9

LOGICA: Drag&Drop v.2

GAMES RULES: Drag and drop words in the proper box

QUESTION: Identify autonomous and remote-control vehicles

AUV	autonomous
USV	autonomous
drifter	autonomous
glider	autonomous
ROV	remote-control
Drone	remote-control

OBJ 1 – 7

LOGICA: Drag&Drop v.2

GAMES RULES: Drag and drop words in the proper box

QUESTION: Identify observable variables (directly measurable with sensors) and the not ones.

Temperature	observables
Gravity force	observables
Pressure	observables
Sediment	not measureable
Zooplankton composition	not measureable
Polar Ice stratification	not measureable

OBJECTIVE THREE

Now it's the time to remember that the scientific method uses different approaches to give explanations to observations. So, identify the measurement methods and recognize the temporal or spatial variability of the parameters. You now need to become an expert in recognizing measurement methods.

GAME RULES
Choose the correct answer

QUESTION
Recognize qualitative or quantitative situations.

Relative mean organism size of phytoplankton dominant shapes in coastal waters (Italy)

Cerathium candelabrum(Ehr) Stein 1883

QUANTITATIVE QUALITATIVE BOTH

CHECK CONTINUE

OBJ 3 - 4

LOGICA: Short Question

GAMES RULES: Choose the correct answer

QUESTION: Identify the measurement method: Lagrangian or Eulerian

The different measurement methods can be classified in Lagrangian and Eulerian:
 Lagrangian methods: the instrument follows an individual fluid parcel as it moves through space and time and measures the time variations of one or more variables.

Eulerian methods: the instrument is fixed in a site and measures one or more variables in the space around it.

Fig 6

Lagrangian 6

Eulerian

Figures References:

[6] Poulain, P.-M., Barbanti, R., Font, J., Cruzado, A., Millot, C., et al.. MedArgo: a drifting profiler program in the Mediterranean Sea. Ocean Science, European Geosciences Union, 2007, 3 (3), pp.379-395. <hal-00331145>

GAME RULES
Choose the correct answer

QUESTION
Recognize qualitative or quantitative situations.

Relative mean organism size of phytoplankton dominant shapes in coastal waters (Italy)

Ceratum candidabrum(Ehr.) Stein 1883

QUANTITATIVE QUALITATIVE BOTH

CHECK CONTINUE

OBJ 3 - 4

LOGICA: Short Question

GAMES RULES: Choose the correct answer

QUESTION: Identify the measurement method: Lagrangian or Eulerian

The different measurement methods can be classified in Lagrangian and Eulerian:
Lagrangian methods: the instrument follows an individual fluid parcel as it moves through space and time and measures the time variations of one or more variables.

Eulerian methods: the instrument is fixed in a site and measures one or more variables in the space around it.

Fig 7

Lagrangian

Eulerian 7

Figures References:

[7] B. Manca, M. Burca, A. Giorgetti, C. Coatanoan, M.-J. Garcia, A. Iona, 2004. Journal of Marine Systems 48, 83–116. doi:10.1016/j.jmarsys.2003.11.025

OBJ 3 - 4

LOGICA: Short Question

GAMES RULES: Choose the correct answer

QUESTION: Identify remote or in situ measurement

Satellites are important platforms for the ocean observation. By remotely sensing satellites provide a lot information about: ocean bathymetry, sea surface temperature, ocean color, coral reefs, sea and lake ice, ... Satellite data need to be calibrate by reference measurements: in situ data.

In situ measurements, not only are necessary to calibrate the satellite data, but mostly provide the variability along the whole column of water from the surface to the sea bottom. The in situ measurements are acquired by several kind of instrument and platforms autonomous or not. The acquisition quality protocols are used to ensure the comparability of data.

Fig. 8b

Remote measurements

In situ measurements 8b

Figures References:

[8] Locritani, M., Gasparini, G.P., Carmisciano, C., castellano, M., Povero, P., 2011. The driving forces of the biotic processes along an offshore gradient in the Liguria basin (Portofino Promontory), during 2008. Geophysical Research Abstracts, Vol. 13, EGU2011-13102, EGU General Assembly 2011.

OBJ 3 - 4

LOGICA: Short Question

GAMES RULES: Choose the correct answer

QUESTION: Identify remote or in situ measurement

Satellites are important platforms for the ocean observation. By remotely sensing satellites provide a lot information about: ocean bathymetry, sea surface temperature, ocean color, coral reefs, sea and lake ice, ... Satellite data need to be calibrate by reference measurements: in situ data.

In situ measurements, not only are necessary to calibrate the satellite data, but mostly provide the variability along the whole column of water from the surface to the sea bottom. The in situ measurements are acquired by several kind of instrument and platforms autonomous or not. The acquisition quality protocols are used to ensure the comparability of data.

Fig. 8a

Remote measurements 8a

In situ measurements

Figures References:

[8] Locritani, M., Gasparini, G.P., Carmisciano, C., castellano, M., Povero, P., 2011. The driving forces of the biotic processes along an offshore gradient in the Ligurina basin (Portofino Promontory), during 2008. Geophysical Research Abstracts, Vol. 13, EGU2011-13102, EGU General Assembly 2011.

GAME RULES
Match each item with the corresponding rank

19 / 28
Objective 1 | Objective 2 | **Objective 3**

QUESTION
Distinguish Null and Alternative Hypotheses.

	Species richness varies among sites	Alternative
	Species richness varies among habitat types in lagoons	Alternative
	Individual size varies among conditions	Null
	Species richness does not vary among habitats/conditions /pressures	Alternative

CHECK CONTINUE

OBJ 3 -1

LOGICA: Drag&drop

GAMES RULES: Drag and drop images in the proper box

QUESTION: Identify the general relation expected between different variables

Water density versus water temperature

inversely proportional

Water density versus water salinity

directly proportional

Water density versus water depth

directly proportional

OBJ 3 - 4

LOGICA: Short Question

GAMES RULES: Choose the correct answer

QUESTION: Identify spatial and temporal variability

Fig. 4, 5b

Temporal variability

Spatial variability 4, 5b

Both

GAME RULES
Choose the correct answer

QUESTION
Recognize qualitative or quantitative situations.

Mean Organism Size (µm)
Shape code

Relative mean organism size of phytoplankton dominant shapes in coastal waters (Italy)

Ceratium candelabrum(Ehr.) Stein 1883

QUANTITATIVE QUALITATIVE BOTH

CHECK CONTINUE

Figures References:

[4] - Locritani et al., 2018. The environmental characterization of Lake Vättern and the AUV test for the Clean Sea project. Rapporti Tecnici INGV.

[5] Locritani, M., Chiappini, O., Chiarabini, R., Bruni, F., Ciccarelli, V., Natale, L., De Paulis, R., 2010. Hydrological and physical characterization of Cinque Terre Marine Protected Area (Ligurian Sea) and evaluation of current velocity and direction by AUV navigation tracks. OCEANS2010, extended abstract. Doi:

GAME RULES
Choose the correct answer

Objective 1 | Objective 2 | **Objective 3**

QUESTION
Recognize qualitative or quantitative situations.

Relative mean organism size of phytoplankton dominant shapes in coastal waters (Italy)

Ceratium candelabrum(Ehr.) Stein 1883

OBJ 3 - 4

LOGICA: Short Question

GAMES RULES: Choose the correct answer

QUESTION: Identify spatial and temporal variability

Fig. 5a

Temporal variability 5a

Spatial variability

Figures References:

[4] - Locritani et al., 2018. The environmental characterization of Lake Vättern and the AUV test for the Clean Sea project. Rapporti Tecnici INGV.

[5] Locritani, M., Chiappini, O., Chiarabini, R., Bruni, F., Ciccarelli, V., Natale, L., De Paulis, R., 2010. Hydrological and physical characterization of Cinque Terre Marine Protected Area (Ligurian Sea) and evaluation of current velocity and direction by AUV navigation tracks. OCEANS2010, extended abstract. Doi: 10.1109/OCEANS.2010.5664052

GAME RULES
Choose the correct answer

22 / 28
Objective 1 | Objective 2 | **Objective 3**

QUESTION
Recognize qualitative or quantitative situations.

Relative mean organism size of phytoplankton dominant shapes in coastal waters (Italy)

Ceratium candelebrum(Ehr.) Stein 1883

QUANTITATIVE
 QUALITATIVE
 BOTH

OBJ 3 - 4

LOGICA: Short Question

GAMES RULES: Choose the correct answer

QUESTION: Identify the kind of measurement

Fig. 1

Temperature Vertical Profiles made by CTD 1

Temperature acquired by Autonomous Underwater Vehicle

Figures References:

[1] - Chierici et al., 2016. A new method to assess long-term sea-bottom vertical displacement in shallow water using a bottom pressure sensor: Application to Campi Flegrei, Southern Italy. Journal of Geophysical Research.

GAME RULES
Choose the correct answer

22 / 28
Objective 1 | Objective 2 | **Objective 3**

QUESTION
Recognize qualitative or quantitative situations.

Relative mean organism size of phytoplankton dominant shapes in coastal waters (Italy)

Cerathium candelabrum(Ehr.) Stein 1883

QUANTITATIVE QUALITATIVE BOTH

OBJ 3 - 4

LOGICA: Short Question

GAMES RULES: Choose the correct answer

QUESTION: Identify the kind of measurement

Fig. 3

Velocity field by Numerical Model 3

Trajectories of Drifters

Figures References:

[3] Haza et al., 2010. Transport properties in small-scale coastal flows: relative dispersion from VHF radar measurements in the Gulf of La Spezia. Ocean Dynamics.

GAME RULES
Choose the correct answer

22 / 28
Objective 1 | Objective 2 | **Objective 3**

QUESTION
Recognize qualitative or quantitative situations.

Relative mean organism size of phytoplankton dominant shapes in coastal waters (Italy)

Cerathium candelabrum(Ehr.) Stein 1883

QUANTITATIVE QUALITATIVE BOTH

OBJ 3 - 4

LOGICA: Short Question

GAMES RULES: Choose the correct answer

QUESTION: Identify the kind of measurement

Fig. 2

Trajectories of Drifters 2

Horizontal temperature transects

Figures References:

[2] - [Ruo-ShanTseng](#), [Yung-TingShen](#), 2003. Lagrangian observations of surface flow patterns in the vicinity of Taiwan. Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography. [Volume 50, Issues 6–7](#), Pages 1107-1115

